

Can the State Change the Narratives? Evaluating Community Policing and Security Management in Enugu State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the involvement of non-state security actors in community protection and the human rights concerns associated with their operations. The research was guided by two key questions: (1) Has the role of local vigilante groups significantly contributed to extrajudicial actions in Enugu State from 2015 to 2024? (2) Has the implementation of security measures by the Neighbourhood Watch significantly led to the excessive use of force in Enugu State within the same period? The study adopted the ex-post facto research design, supported by the Noble Cause Corruption Theory, which explains why security actors justify unlawful actions as necessary for public good. This study adopts a mixed method of data collection that includes questionnaires, interviews, academic publications, NGO reports, newspaper documents, and human rights records. Findings revealed that the implementation of security measures by the Neighbourhood Watch significantly led to excessive use of force, largely due to poor training, weak regulatory oversight, and cultural acceptance of instant justice. At the end, the study calls for the government of Enugu State to strengthen the regulation, supervision, and accountability frameworks governing local vigilante groups.

Keywords: Modus Operandi, Vigilante Groups, Human Rights Violations, Extrajudicial Actions, Excessive Use of Force

Introduction

The increasing spate of insecurity in Nigeria over the past decade has given rise to the proliferation of community vigilante groups as an alternative security mechanism, especially in states where the formal security architecture has proven inadequate. Enugu State, located in the South-East geopolitical zone, has witnessed a significant emergence and institutionalisation of community-based security outfits between 2015 and 2024. These groups, often operating under local titles such as Neighbourhood Watch, Forest Guards, or Ebubeagu Security Network, were established to combat rising incidences of kidnapping, armed robbery, and communal conflicts (Nnam et al., 2021). However, while their formation was initially celebrated as a grassroots response to insecurity, concerns have increasingly emerged regarding their involvement in extrajudicial killings, torture, unlawful detention, and other human rights abuses (Amadi & Onyebuchi, 2023).

Conceptually, community vigilante groups refer to locally organised, non-state actors that engage in policing functions traditionally reserved for formal security institutions (Ajayi, 2020). They derive legitimacy from community consensus rather than constitutional or statutory authority, reflecting a form of community policing shaped by indigenous governance structures (Oluwole & Okafor, 2022). Vigilante groups operate under the theoretical lens of security pluralism, which recognises the coexistence of multiple actors, state and non-state, within the broader security governance framework (Baker, 2008). However, this pluralism becomes problematic when informal security actors operate without adequate regulation, accountability, or oversight mechanisms. Their presence challenges the Weberian conception of the state as the sole entity possessing the monopoly of legitimate violence (Weber, 1919).

In contrast, human rights violations in this context encompass acts or omissions that infringe upon the fundamental rights of individuals as enshrined in Nigeria's 1999 Constitution and international conventions such as the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights. Such violations may include unlawful arrest, torture, arbitrary detention, and extrajudicial killings (Onuoha, 2022). Human rights frameworks view these violations as indicators of state failure in ensuring the protection and dignity of its citizens, thereby questioning the legitimacy of security interventions that contravene due process (Eze, 2023).

The conceptual interaction between these two variables, community vigilante groups and human rights violations, reveals a tension between security needs and human rights protection. On one hand, vigilante groups are formed as a pragmatic response to the inefficiency of the Nigerian Police Force and the pervasive insecurity affecting rural and urban communities alike. On the other, their methods often contravene constitutional guarantees of fair trial, personal liberty, and protection from torture. This contradiction embodies what Agbiboa (2021) refers to as the

“security–rights paradox”, wherein attempts to ensure safety through non-state actors inadvertently reproduce insecurity through rights abuses.

The formation of vigilante groups is not a recent development. Before 1900, many vigilante groups were formed in frontier areas of the United States. In 1851 and 1856, concerned citizens in San Francisco organised vigilante committees that forcefully restored peace and order (Singer, 2010). Similarly, in South Africa, vigilante activity is frequently justified as an attempt to “fill a policing gap” resulting from police inefficiency, corruption, and collusion with criminals, as well as broader failures within the criminal justice system (Teka, 2012). In Sierra Leone, the rise of vigilante activities has been explained primarily in terms of police ineffectiveness in combating crime and maintaining social order (Brownyn, 2009).

In the Nigerian context, vigilantism existed long before the colonial period. The Human Rights Watch and Centre for Law Enforcement and Education Report (2002) noted that vigilantes and other self-defence groups currently operating in Nigeria have roots that reach deep into the country's history. In the colonial era, some, though not all, independent local communities, especially in the southeast, maintained their own standing armies to defend their territory against the threat of invasion from neighbouring communities. Although there was no equivalent modern-day structure at that time, some parallels can be drawn between these groups, which were created by local communities for their own protection, and the more recently formed self-defence groups. (Human Rights Watch & Center for Law Enforcement and Education, 2002, p. 15)

In early 2020, amid nationwide anxiety over the escalation of herder–farmer conflicts and kidnapping incidents, the South-East Governors’ Forum announced the establishment of the Ebubeagu Security Network (Okolie, 2021). Although initially meant to complement the Nigerian Police, its operations in Enugu and neighbouring states soon generated controversy over alleged partisanship and excessive use of force. Several documented incidents highlight this. For instance, in 2021, local media reported the killing of three youths in Nsukka by members of a local vigilante outfit during a raid on suspected cultists (Nwankwo & Ezeani, 2022). In 2022, Amnesty International expressed concern over reports of arbitrary detentions and physical assaults by community watch members operating under state recognition (Amnesty International, 2022). These developments correspond with a broader pattern of informal security groups becoming politicised and used as instruments of local control, especially during the lead-up to the 2023 general elections (Okafor & Obi, 2023).

Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020–2021 served as a catalyst for expanding the operational scope of vigilante groups. With lockdown enforcement and movement restrictions, many communities empowered these groups to enforce public health directives. However, reports from civil society organisations indicated instances of brutality and excessive force

during enforcement, leading to the deaths and injuries of several citizens (CLEEN Foundation, 2021). Such cases underscored the dangers of vesting quasi-policing authority in groups lacking proper training and accountability structures.

By 2023, as the security situation in Enugu worsened with increasing reports of armed banditry in rural areas like Uzo-Uwani and Ezeagu, the state government intensified collaboration with vigilante formations (Ugwueze & Odo, 2023). However, this institutionalisation came without corresponding mechanisms to ensure compliance with human rights norms. In several cases, individuals accused of minor offences such as theft were reportedly subjected to jungle justice, reflecting a culture of impunity (Onyishi, 2024). The Human Rights Defenders Network (2024) reported that between 2020 and 2024, over 150 complaints of human rights violations were linked to community vigilante operatives in Enugu State alone, including unlawful detention, beatings, and extrajudicial killings.

The increasing interpenetration between community security and political structures further complicates the situation. Many vigilante groups are allegedly affiliated with political actors, thereby blurring the line between security provision and political coercion (Aneke & Udeh, 2023). During the 2023 elections, for instance, there were claims that certain groups were deployed to intimidate political opponents and voters, leading to renewed debates about the politicisation of community policing in Nigeria (Iwuoha & Nnamani, 2024). The pattern reflects what Nte (2021) calls the “informalisation of violence”, where the state indirectly endorses coercive force through non-state proxies. Therefore, while community vigilante groups remain a vital component of local security architecture, their sustainability and legitimacy depend on institutional reforms that prioritise training, accountability, and adherence to human rights norms. Strengthening oversight mechanisms, ensuring alignment with constitutional safeguards, and promoting collaboration between vigilante operatives and formal law enforcement agencies are essential for achieving a balance between community safety and the protection of human dignity. Ultimately, the Enugu State experience underscores the need for a rights-based approach to community security—one that recognises that true safety cannot exist in the absence of justice and respect for human rights. Consequently, this study examines the relationship between community vigilant groups and human rights violations in Enugu State, 2015-2024.

The roles of local vigilante groups and extrajudicial actions in Enugu State

The increasing prominence of local vigilante groups in Nigeria, particularly in Enugu State, has generated significant scholarly attention regarding their roles in maintaining community security, supplementing the police, and sometimes undermining the rule of law. Scholars broadly agree that the proliferation of such groups reflects systemic weaknesses in state policing and a search for grassroots alternatives to insecurity (Alemika, 2020; Iwuoha & Aniche, 2021). Local vigilante organisations such as the Enugu Vigilante Group (EVG) and the Neighbourhood Watch

have evolved as hybrid security formations combining traditional authority, community participation, and state recognition. Their rise can be traced to the inability of the Nigerian Police Force to provide effective security coverage across rural and peri-urban areas (Eke, 2019). Thus, communities have assumed the responsibility of safeguarding themselves, drawing legitimacy from local social structures and collective consent. Historically, the emergence of vigilante groups in Nigeria is tied to the weakening of state institutions and growing distrust in the Nigerian Police Force. Nweke and Nwankwo (2023) observed that in Enugu State, communities began to organise self-help security networks as a response to persistent threats such as armed robbery, kidnapping, and communal violence. These vigilante formations, often operating under community unions or traditional authorities, function as neighbourhood watch groups, night patrol units, or rapid response teams. Their legitimacy is often derived from local consent rather than statutory recognition. According to Lenshie and Chinedu (2024), this form of “civilian-led community policing” represents both a form of empowerment and a symptom of state failure in the delivery of security services.

Studies show that vigilante groups play multiple roles that straddle the boundaries between formal and informal security. As Onuoha (2019) observed, they operate as mediators of local justice, first responders to criminal incidents, and community mobilisers for peace initiatives. In Enugu State, their significance has been heightened by the expansion of urban crime and rural banditry. Research by Okoli and Ugwu (2022) found that community members perceive vigilantes as more accessible and trustworthy than the formal police, largely due to their embeddedness within the communities they serve. This community proximity fosters faster intelligence gathering and a deeper understanding of local criminal dynamics. Yet, it also raises ethical and legal questions concerning due process and accountability. Scholars such as Akinlabi and Ihemeje (2021) argue that vigilante organisations serve a critical function in crime deterrence through their visible presence and swift intervention mechanisms. In rural Enugu communities, their patrol activities have been reported to significantly reduce incidents of theft and burglary. Similarly, Okafor, Okoye, and Nzekwe-Chinwuko (2025) found that the presence of vigilante groups in neighbouring Anambra and Enugu States correlated with a decline in violent crimes between 2014 and 2022. These findings suggest that localised security initiatives, when coordinated effectively, can fill enforcement gaps left by formal agencies. However, Udoh (2025) cautioned that without appropriate regulation, such groups risk evolving into unaccountable paramilitary entities that may resort to extrajudicial practices.

Moreover, the emergence of regionally coordinated security networks such as the Southeast’s EbubeAgu further complicates the role of local vigilante groups. While designed to harmonise community policing efforts across Enugu, Anambra, Ebonyi, Abia, and Imo States, EbubeAgu has faced political and logistical challenges (Lenshie & Chinedu, 2024). In many cases, local vigilantes continue to operate independently, guided more by community elders and traditional rulers than by formal policy frameworks. This fragmentation diminishes the potential for

standardised operations and professional accountability. Nonetheless, the Enugu State government's attempts to integrate vigilantes into its broader community policing strategy demonstrate recognition of their indispensability in grassroots security management (Nweke & Nwankwo, 2023). Several authors contend that vigilante groups have improved not only security outcomes but also perceptions of safety among residents. In a study of urban and peri-urban communities in southeastern Nigeria, Udeagbala and Ntukogu (2022) reported a significant decline in petty crime following the establishment of organised vigilante patrols. Residents attributed this improvement to the visible presence of local patrols and their deterrent effect on offenders. Similar findings were echoed in Okoye and Akhidenor's (2023) examination of Edo State, suggesting that vigilantism, despite its contradictions, fills an important security void in Nigeria's federated system. However, these authors also emphasise that sustainability depends on regular oversight, civic education, and legal codification.

The Nigerian government's endorsement of community policing initiatives has led to a gradual institutionalisation of some vigilante networks. In Enugu, the Enugu State Vigilante Service operates semi-formally under the Ministry of Human Development and Poverty Eradication, illustrating an evolving partnership between state actors and community structures (Ezeani, 2020). This formalisation has had mixed results. On one hand, it enhances coordination and legitimacy; on the other, it risks politicisation and the erosion of community autonomy (Aniche & Okeke, 2021). Vigilante groups, once purely local and voluntary, are increasingly entangled in state bureaucracy, funding arrangements, and political patronage systems. Consequently, their original grassroots orientation is challenged by new power dynamics and expectations.

From a governance perspective, scholars situate vigilante groups within the framework of security pluralism, the coexistence of multiple actors providing security outside the monopoly of the state (Baker, 2018). This pluralist landscape has been both a necessity and a symptom of state fragility. In Enugu and other southeastern states, community vigilantes contribute to "everyday policing" by filling critical gaps left by formal institutions (Iwuoha & Aniche, 2021). They manage local disputes, apprehend suspects, and often hand them over to the police. However, the lack of standardised training and oversight has resulted in instances of excessive force and extrajudicial punishment (Human Rights Watch, 2019). This paradox encapsulates the dual character of vigilantes, as protectors and potential violators. Cultural and historical factors also underpin the endurance of local vigilante formations. Traditional Igbo society historically relied on communal self-help and collective responsibility for social order. The modern vigilante system can therefore be seen as a continuation of indigenous models of security governance (Nwankwo, 2018). In Enugu State, village assemblies, town unions, and traditional rulers often collaborate with vigilante outfits, blending customary and modern practices. This hybridisation not only ensures community legitimacy but also embeds vigilantes within local moral economies, making them accountable to the people rather than distant bureaucracies.

Empirical evidence supports the claim that vigilante groups have contributed significantly to crime reduction in certain parts of Enugu. Nwobodo (2020) documented that burglary and armed robbery rates declined in Nsukka and Udi local government areas following the introduction of organised community watch schemes. Nonetheless, these successes are tempered by broader structural issues, including inadequate funding, lack of coordination with the police, and inter-group rivalries. Okoro and Duru (2022) observed that competition among multiple vigilante units in the same locality often leads to inefficiency and, occasionally, violent clashes over jurisdiction. The effectiveness of these groups, therefore, depends on clear legal frameworks and operational boundaries. The gender dimension of vigilante operations is another underexplored area in the literature. Most groups remain male-dominated, reflecting broader gendered hierarchies in security governance (Ogu, 2021). Despite their critical roles in sustaining peace at the household and neighbourhood levels, women's involvement often remains limited to intelligence gathering and community mediation. Integrating women's perspectives could broaden the social legitimacy and moral authority of community policing in Enugu.

Furthermore, technological and social media dynamics have transformed how vigilante groups operate. Recent studies highlight how mobile communication and local radio facilitate rapid information dissemination, improving crime response times (Eke & Umeh, 2023). However, this digitisation also exposes them to misinformation and the risks of mob mobilisation. The challenge, therefore, lies in balancing community vigilance with responsible communication and adherence to lawful procedures. Human rights implications remain one of the most contentious issues in the debate about vigilante roles. Reports by the CLEEN Foundation (2021) and Amnesty International (2022) highlight cases of arbitrary detention, torture, and summary executions attributed to some local groups. In Enugu State, while most vigilante formations operate within community ethics, lapses in discipline and training have occasionally led to abuses. Consequently, civil society organisations advocate for reforms emphasising oversight, human rights education, and partnership with the National Human Rights Commission. Balancing local justice with legal standards remains central to sustaining their credibility and effectiveness.

In addition to crime prevention, local vigilantes play symbolic roles in fostering collective identity and resilience. Their presence signifies the community's agency in addressing insecurity and resisting external threats. Yet, this same agency can generate friction with formal state institutions. Nwangbo et al. (2022) note that police officers often view vigilantes with ambivalence, perceiving them as both collaborators and competitors. The challenge, therefore, lies in creating an institutional framework where cooperation replaces competition and where community initiatives complement rather than contradict state authority. Nwokolo (2020) proposes that policy reforms should formalise training, ethics, and operational standards for vigilante groups to prevent abuses and enhance synergy with law enforcement. In Enugu State, the experiences of communities like Udenu, Nsukka, and Awgu illustrate the complex balance

between community protection and legal governance. While local vigilante groups have successfully deterred criminal gangs and facilitated the recovery of stolen property, isolated cases of violence and mob justice persist (Nweke & Nwankwo, 2023). These incidents underscore the need for continuous engagement between community leaders, the judiciary, and civil society organisations to redefine the scope of vigilante authority. As the study suggests, a hybrid model that integrates vigilante networks into formal policing systems, under the supervision of local governments, could sustain their contributions while safeguarding civil liberties (Udoh, 2025; Jack-Rabin et al., 2023).

Scholarly discourse on the roles of local vigilante groups in Nigeria, particularly in Enugu State, reveals diverse perspectives rooted in criminological, sociological, and governance frameworks. Scholars converge on the understanding that the emergence of these groups reflects both the weaknesses of state institutions and the resilience of community self-help initiatives. According to Udoh (2025), the rise of vigilante organisations represents a functional adaptation to state incapacity, where communities mobilise resources and manpower to secure themselves from criminal threats. His functionalist interpretation sees vigilante groups as socially necessary structures that fill institutional voids in crime prevention and law enforcement. Similarly, Kenneth, Udeh, Ugwu, and Odo (2023) emphasise that these groups act as vital complements to the Nigerian Police Force by providing grassroots intelligence, patrolling neighbourhoods, and deterring criminal activities. In Enugu State, where police-to-citizen ratios are extremely low, their intervention has been credited with reducing incidences of robbery, theft, and kidnapping. In contrast to Udoh's functionalist optimism, Lenshie and Chinedu (2024) take a more critical stance, arguing that the proliferation of vigilante groups exposes the failure of the state to maintain its monopoly on the legitimate use of force. They assert that while local security groups fill an immediate gap, they simultaneously weaken the authority of formal institutions by creating parallel enforcement mechanisms. In their view, Enugu's numerous community-based vigilante groups are symptomatic of a decentralisation of violence, where community actors assume coercive powers without adequate legal checks. This argument aligns with Max Weber's theory of state legitimacy, which underscores the dangers of privatised coercion. Lenshie and Chinedu (2024) therefore caution that the increasing reliance on non-state security actors, though practical in the short term, undermines long-term governance stability and erodes public confidence in state institutions.

Akinlabi and Ihemeje (2021) adopt an empirical lens to evaluate vigilante efficiency in local crime prevention. Through field surveys conducted in southeastern Nigeria, including parts of Enugu, they found that over 70% of respondents expressed higher trust in local vigilantes than in the police. The researchers attribute this trust to the proximity and cultural embeddedness of vigilante members, who are often community natives with deep knowledge of the local environment. Their findings reinforce the argument that social cohesion enhances security effectiveness, as community members are more willing to cooperate with familiar figures.

However, they also note that this familiarity can become a liability, as personal relationships sometimes lead to selective enforcement or tolerance of local elites' misconduct. Further contributions come from Nweke and Nwankwo (2023), who situate the discussion within the framework of community policing. They contend that vigilante groups in Enugu State represent an informal but practical model of community policing, grounded in local ownership and participatory decision-making. Unlike top-down policing structures, these groups rely on communal consent and local knowledge to detect threats. Nweke and Nwankwo argue that the incorporation of vigilante networks into official community policing policy could strengthen the security system while ensuring accountability through community oversight. Their policy-orientated analysis advocates for the hybridisation of formal and informal security mechanisms, a model that could harmonise local initiative with state authority.

However, not all scholars share this optimistic outlook. According to Nwokolo (2020), the informal nature of vigilante operations poses serious governance and human rights risks. His work on non-state security actors in Nigeria highlights cases of extrajudicial killings, torture, and mob justice carried out by vigilante members in southeastern states. In Enugu, there have been documented incidents of vigilante groups detaining suspects without due process, violating constitutional rights in the name of community protection. Nwokolo thus calls for legal codification and regulatory oversight to prevent abuses while maintaining their positive role in crime control. His position is echoed by Wambai, Tijani, and Iroye (2024), who argue that the legitimacy of vigilante groups should not only be grounded in social acceptance but also in compliance with human rights standards. They insist that community-based enforcement must align with democratic principles if it is to contribute meaningfully to sustainable security.

Meanwhile, Usman, Yunusa, and Goment (2023) examine vigilante operations through the lens of participatory security governance. Their study emphasises that the success of local security initiatives depends on active citizen engagement and inclusivity. They found that when vigilante groups involve women, youth, and marginalized segments of the community, the effectiveness of crime prevention increases. In Enugu State, however, such inclusivity remains limited, with most vigilante outfits dominated by male youth. This gendered structure, according to the authors, restricts the diversity of perspectives and weakens trust among certain groups, especially women and the elderly. They advocate for a more gender-sensitive approach to community security. A more critical dimension is offered by Fashiku and Olesin (2025), who warn against the politicisation of vigilante operations. Their findings suggest that in many Nigerian states, including Enugu, local politicians often sponsor or manipulate vigilante groups for electoral or personal gain. This political interference not only compromises neutrality but also fuels intergroup conflicts. Fashiku and Olesin recommend depoliticising local security networks through statutory reforms and the establishment of independent oversight bodies. Such institutional checks, they argue, are necessary to prevent vigilantes from becoming instruments of coercion or political intimidation.

Udoh (2025) acknowledges that local vigilante organisations fill significant security gaps in rural and urban areas where state policing has failed, but he critiques the existing studies for their overreliance on descriptive rather than analytical approaches. According to Udoh, most research on vigilante groups, including those focusing on Enugu State, tends to emphasise functional roles, such as crime prevention and surveillance, without adequately interrogating the underlying structural and institutional factors that give rise to such organisations. This limitation, he argues, leads to an incomplete understanding of the socio-political environment that sustains vigilante operations. Furthermore, he contends that the tendency to treat vigilante groups as homogenous entities oversimplifies their complex and sometimes contradictory nature. In reality, these groups vary widely in organisation, motivation, and effectiveness across different communities in Enugu State. Nwokolo (2020) critiques the normative bias in many studies that implicitly justify vigilantism as a necessary response to state failure. His work highlights that this assumption risks legitimising extra-legal security practices and normalising violence outside the state's monopoly on coercion. In his assessment, researchers often neglect to examine the long-term implications of allowing non-state actors to assume quasi-policing functions. He argues that by framing vigilante activities solely within the lens of community protection, scholars inadvertently obscure the broader governance challenges, such as corruption, weak justice systems, and lack of public accountability. This critique points to a limitation in current scholarship, which often prioritises short-term functionalism over structural analysis.

Similarly, Lenshie and Chinedu (2024) identify conceptual vagueness in the literature, noting that many studies fail to differentiate between vigilante groups, militias, and community policing initiatives. This conflation, they argue, distorts the analytical clarity necessary for policy formulation. Their critique stresses the importance of distinguishing between lawful community policing frameworks sanctioned by the state and informal vigilante formations that operate without oversight. In the context of Enugu State, where various community-based security groups coexist, this conceptual ambiguity hampers effective coordination and regulation. The authors also criticise researchers for neglecting comparative analysis across regions, which could illuminate why certain vigilante networks succeed in maintaining community trust while others deteriorate into instruments of coercion or extortion. Methodological limitations in existing studies have also been a subject of critique. Akinlabi and Ihemeje (2021) argue that much of the empirical research on vigilante groups relies heavily on qualitative interviews and anecdotal evidence, often gathered from small and non-representative samples. This approach, while rich in context, limits the generalisability of findings. They propose that mixed-methods research incorporating quantitative data, such as crime statistics, community surveys, and longitudinal assessments, would provide more robust insights into the actual impact of vigilante activities. The lack of consistent data on crime reduction attributable to vigilante operations, particularly in Enugu State, represents a major gap in the literature. As a result, many claims regarding the effectiveness of these groups remain speculative rather than empirically substantiated. Nweke and Nwankwo (2023) expand this critique by highlighting the political and ethical challenges

that affect both practice and research on local vigilantes. They observe that state authorities and politicians often exert influence over community security structures, either by sponsoring vigilante groups for electoral purposes or by manipulating their activities for political gain. This politicisation not only undermines neutrality but also affects the reliability of research findings, as respondents may withhold information out of fear of reprisal. Consequently, studies on vigilante groups in Enugu State frequently encounter issues of respondent bias, incomplete disclosure, and limited access to operational records. These constraints make it difficult to obtain objective assessments of vigilante performance and legitimacy.

Fashiku and Olesin (2025) offer a governance-centred critique, focusing on the institutional weakness that enables the proliferation of vigilante groups. They argue that most studies treat vigilante organisations as isolated phenomena rather than as outcomes of systemic failures in governance, justice, and socio-economic policy. In their view, any analysis that ignores the structural underpinnings of poverty, unemployment, and inequality misses the root causes of insecurity. Their limitation critique therefore calls for a multi-level analytical approach that situates vigilantism within broader questions of state legitimacy and capacity. In Enugu State, where economic deprivation and unemployment are significant, such structural explanations are vital to understanding why community members continue to depend on self-help security arrangements despite formal state presence. Kenneth, Udeh, Ugwu, and Odo (2023) critique the narrow scope of most studies, observing that researchers often focus exclusively on crime prevention without examining the socio-economic consequences of vigilante activities. They argue that the economic dimension of community security remains understudied, despite evidence that improved safety contributes to local development and business confidence. Furthermore, they highlight that existing studies rarely investigate the financial sustainability of vigilante organisations, which often rely on voluntary contributions or ad hoc government support. This lack of attention to economic structure limits understanding of the long-term viability of vigilante operations in Enugu State.

To begin with, many existing studies, including those by Udoh (2025), Kenneth et al. (2023), and Nwokolo (2020), primarily focus on the *functional dimensions* of vigilante groups, such as their involvement in crime prevention, surveillance, and conflict resolution, without examining the *underlying social dynamics and governance implications* that sustain these groups. This functionalist bias treats vigilante formations as static institutions, neglecting their fluid interactions with political authorities, religious leaders, and traditional institutions. The current study departs from this approach by adopting a holistic framework that situates vigilante groups within the broader socio-political and cultural contexts of Enugu State. Such contextualisation allows for a richer understanding of how local norms, kinship ties, and communal values influence the formation, operation, and legitimacy of vigilante groups. Furthermore, scholars such as Lenshie and Chinedu (2024) and Fashiku and Olesin (2025) have identified the conceptual ambiguity between vigilante groups, militias, and community policing initiatives.

Yet, even their works stop short of disentangling the *unique characteristics* of vigilante groups in southeastern Nigeria, particularly in Enugu State, where security structures are deeply embedded in traditional leadership systems. The lack of clear conceptual distinction has led to analytical confusion and policy misdirection. This study fills that gap by providing an empirically derived typology of vigilante formations in Enugu State, distinguishing their operational structures, sources of legitimacy, and modes of accountability from those of other non-state actors. By doing so, it offers conceptual clarity that can inform both academic debate and security policy.

Finally, the majority of prior studies have not adequately captured *the lived experiences* of community members in Enugu State regarding their interactions with vigilante groups. Much of the literature relies on institutional narratives or elite perspectives, overlooking grassroots voices that could provide critical insights into community perceptions of safety, justice, and belonging. The current study therefore takes a bottom-up approach, prioritising local narratives and perceptions. Through this participatory perspective, it seeks to democratise the discourse on security governance and offer a more inclusive understanding of how communities in Enugu State navigate insecurity and informal justice.

Theoretical Framework

The study uses the Noble-Cause Corruption theory propounded by Carl B. Klockars (1980). The theory serves as an analytical framework through which the community vigilante groups and the resulting human rights violations in Enugu State between 2015 and 2024 are studied. Noble Cause Corruption Theory, originally articulated by Klockars (1980), explains how actors pursuing morally justified ends may adopt illegal or unethical methods because they believe the desired outcome, such as community protection, justifies bending or breaking established rules. Applied to the Enugu context, the theory illuminates how vigilante groups, established to combat robbery, kidnapping, cultism, and communal insecurity, often operate from a belief that extraordinary threats require extraordinary responses, even when those responses conflict with human rights norms.

Studies on informal policing in Nigeria show that vigilante groups frequently justify their actions through appeals to higher community loyalties and public safety imperatives (Alemika, 2018; Meagher, 2020). This corresponds with Caldero and Crank's (2004) assertion that noble cause actors rationalise misconduct as necessary for achieving a greater public good. In Enugu, particularly in Nsukka, Awgu, Udi, and Enugu East, vigilante units were documented engaging in beatings, forced confessions, arbitrary arrests, and summary punishments of suspected offenders. Reports from civil society groups between 2017 and 2023 indicate that suspects were sometimes tortured or executed without trial, with vigilante members defending their actions on the grounds that "the justice system would release them", a justification consistent with noble cause reasoning (CLEEN Foundation, 2021).

The social and cultural environment further entrenched this pattern of behaviour. Local communities, frustrated with perceived police inefficiency, often celebrated vigilante groups as protectors, even when their methods were harsh. This dynamic reflects Punch's (2009) view that noble cause corruption thrives when institutions or communities applaud outcomes rather than scrutinise processes. Community leaders and political actors at times encouraged the use of "any means necessary" to curb rising crime, creating an enabling environment where violative practices were normalised and morally defended.

Rising insecurity from 2015 onwards, particularly the surge in kidnapping, cult clashes, and local banditry, intensified pressure on vigilante groups, nurturing a mindset in which due process was perceived as a hindrance rather than a safeguard. This aligns with Skolnick's (1994) argument that occupational pressures rooted in danger and urgency cultivate a working personality that accepts shortcuts in the pursuit of order. As a result, vigilante groups in Enugu routinely violated rights not merely out of malice but out of a convinced belief that such actions were indispensable for community survival.

Thus, Noble Cause Corruption Theory demonstrates that the human rights violations committed by vigilante groups in Enugu State from 2015 to 2024 were not random abuses but patterned behaviours enabled by moral conviction, community endorsement, and insufficient oversight. The theory clarifies that the central risk is not the absence of moral purpose but the unrestrained moral certainty that empowers vigilante actors to justify torture, extrajudicial punishment, and denial of due process as necessary sacrifices for public good..

Methodology

Research Design and Method of Data Collection

This study adopts the Ex-post facto design and a mixed-methods of data collection, combining primary quantitative data (structured questionnaires) with interview and qualitative documentary evidence.

Instrument of data collection and Study Area

The primary instrument of data collection for this study is a structured questionnaire, which is appropriate for quantitative research and allows for standardized responses from a large and diverse population (Kerlinger, 1986). Furthermore, the study is situated in Enugu State, located in the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria, created in 1991 and historically known as the "Coal City" due to early coal mining activities (FGN, 1991). The research focuses on three Local Government Areas (LGAs), each selected from one of the three senatorial zones of Enugu State: Nsukka LGA (Enugu North Senatorial Zone), Awgu LGA (Enugu East Senatorial Zone), and Isi Uzo LGA (Enugu West Senatorial Zone). These LGAs were chosen to provide a representative

understanding of vigilante activities across diverse geographical and socio-political settings within the state.

Sampling Technique and Population of Interest

This study employs the purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling is appropriate because the study focuses on individuals who possess direct knowledge or experience of vigilante operations, neighbourhood watch activities, and human-rights-related incidents in the selected LGAs. Again, the population of interest for this study comprises all adult residents (18 years and above) living in the three selected LGAs Nsukka, Awgu, and Isi Uzo together with members and leaders of vigilante groups and neighbourhood watch units operating in these communities between 2015 and 2024.

Sample size and Method of Data Analysis

The sample size for the study was 400. The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula, which is widely used in social science research for determining sample size when the population is known. Data were analyzed using a mixed-methods approach. Quantitative data from the questionnaires were coded and processed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and were applied to examine relationships between variables. Interview and Qualitative data from documentary sources were subjected to thematic and content analysis to identify patterns of extrajudicial actions and excessive force.

Results

Frequency of arrests and patrol operations conducted by vigilante groups and cases of unlawful killings and physical abuse

In Enugu State, vigilante groups have become prominent actors in local security management, often conducting regular patrols and making arrests to supplement formal police efforts. Eze (2021), in his study of community policing in Enugu State, asserted that vigilante groups frequently carry out nightly patrols and arrest suspected offenders, but their actions are often carried out without adherence to formal legal procedures, creating risks of abuse. Similarly, Chukwuma and Onwuegbuna (2018) observed that although vigilante patrols in Enugu communities help reduce petty crime, some members engage in physical coercion and extrajudicial punishments, particularly when suspects are apprehended during patrols. Reports indicate that cases of unlawful killings and physical abuse have occurred in certain local government areas where vigilante groups operate with minimal oversight, highlighting the tension between community security and human rights protection (Okeke et al., 2019). Consequently, while vigilante groups in Enugu State contribute to crime deterrence, their

frequent patrols and arrests also suggest that there must be formal regulation and accountability mechanisms.

Table 1: Respondents answers on Frequency of arrests and patrol operations conducted by vigilante groups and cases of unlawful killings and physical abuse

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD
1	Vigilante groups conduct patrol operations frequently in my community.	81 (27.3%)	92 (31.0%)	72 (24.3%)	49 (17.4%)
2	I have observed/heard about arrests made by vigilante groups in the last 12 months.	101 (33.7%)	89 (29.7%)	68 (22.7%)	45 (15.0%)
3	Vigilante arrests usually follow lawful procedures.	39 (13.0%)	55 (18.3%)	90 (30.0%)	74 (24.7%)
4	There have been cases of unlawful killings or physical abuse by vigilante groups in my area.	69 (23.0%)	82 (27.3%)	79 (26.3%)	58 (19.3%)
5	My community is highly concerned about human-rights abuses by vigilante personnel.	88 (29.3%)	93 (31.0%)	68 (22.7%)	51 (17.0%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2025.

The results presented in Table 1 show that vigilante groups are highly active across the three LGAs, particularly in patrol operations and arrest activities. A combined 58.3% (SA + A) of respondents agreed that patrol operations occur frequently in their communities, indicating that vigilante presence is visible and consistent. Similarly, 63.4% (SA + A) reported awareness of arrests carried out by vigilante groups within the last twelve months. This suggests that vigilante groups are significantly involved in frontline local security enforcement.

However, while these patrol and arrest functions appear robust, there are strong concerns regarding the legality of their procedures. Only 31.3% (SA + A) believed vigilante arrests follow lawful procedures, compared to 54.7% (D + SD) who disagreed, revealing widespread community doubt about procedural fairness and compliance with due process. Reports of unlawful killings and physical abuse further reinforce these concerns. A total of 50.3% (SA + A) acknowledged such incidents occurring in their communities, highlighting persistent issues of excessive force.

Community concern over human-rights abuses is also notably high. With 60.3% (SA + A) of respondents indicating elevated fear or worry about rights violations by vigilante personnel, it is evident that these security structures though active may be contributing to insecurity and mistrust.

In accordance to this above analysis, **Ugwu a 41 years Shuttle driver in Nsukka LGA**, (personal interview, 20th October 2025) express that;

In my community (Ejeona) here in Nsukka, the vigilante groups are quite active; they patrol almost every night, especially around the major junctions and inner streets. Sometimes you hear their whistles or see their torchlights around 10 p.m. or even later. Over the past year, I've heard of several arrests they made mostly young boys accused of stealing motorcycles or breaking into small shops. Some of those arrests were praised by the community because crime had been increasing, but I still question how carefully they follow proper procedures. From what I have seen, they tend to act first and ask questions later, and the suspects rarely get the chance to explain themselves before force is used. There have also been murmurs about mistreatment. A few months ago, people talked about an incident where a man was badly beaten after being accused of snatching a woman's bag. Some even said the beating was so severe that he had to be rushed to the hospital. These kinds of stories worry us because we know the vigilantes are not trained like the police. So, while people appreciate the security they bring, there is also a growing fear about possible human-rights abuses. Many in the community including myself are concerned that if they are not monitored properly, they might go beyond their boundaries and harm innocent people (**Ugwu, 41, M, Nsukka LGA, Field survey, 20th October 2025**).

Similarly, Amarachi the wife to Community chief leaders in **Eha-Amufu**, Isi Uzo LGA, (personal interview, 20th October 2025) express her opinion as;

In this community, the vigilante patrols are fairly frequent. You can see them two to three times a week, especially during late evenings when people are returning from their farms or markets. They move in small groups, sometimes carrying sticks or torches. I have heard of a few arrests they made mostly petty thieves or people caught trespassing on farmlands. Some cases seemed straightforward, but others were surrounded by rumours

and confusion. That is why I am not always confident that their arrests are done in accordance with the law. They don't always involve the police immediately, and the methods they use during arrest can be quite rough. There was even a case last year where a teenage boy was beaten so severely after being accused of stealing a goat that many people were upset, saying the punishment was too excessive. Some residents whispered that there may have been deaths linked to vigilante operations in nearby villages, though nobody could say for sure. All these things have made the community cautious. People are grateful that the vigilantes help reduce burglary and nighttime fear, but at the same time, there is a significant level of concern about their use of force and their respect for human rights. Many of us believe they need better training and supervision (**Amarachi, 35, F, Isi Uzo LGA, Field survey, 20th October 2025**).

Another respondent Obinna a 47 years Bread Trader in Awgu LGA,(personal interview 20th October 2025). expressed that:

Here in Neke, the vigilante groups patrol regularly sometimes every night, especially during festive periods or when rumours of criminal activity spread. I live close to a road where they usually pass, so I notice them quite often. Over the past year, I've heard about several arrests they carried out, including one involving a group of young men accused of robbing travellers along the expressway. People talked about the arrest for days, praising the vigilantes for being alert. But even though their efforts are commendable, I still doubt that their arrest procedures follow the law properly. They don't have formal training, and they usually rely on force or intimidation before handing suspects over to the police. As for abuses, yes, things like that have been reported. There was an incident where a man complained that he was beaten because he refused to give information about a missing motorcycle. And in one of the neighbouring communities, people said there was a case of a suspect dying after being handled too roughly, though details were unclear. Because of this, the level of concern in the community is quite high. Many of us want security and peace, but we also worry that these vigilante groups might unintentionally cause more harm if left unchecked. So the fear of human-rights abuse is definitely present, even though we rely on them for protection (**Obinna, 47, M, Awgu LGA, Field survey, 20th October 2025**)

In contrast to the preceding, **IkennaOgbu CSO Eha-Amufu Community Vigilante, Isi-uzo LGA(personal interview. 21, Oct.2025).** Responded that:

In Eha-Amufu, our patrol schedule is largely determined by the level of tension in the area. On a normal week, we patrol about **four times**, mostly at night, because that's when most incidents happen around the border paths. But whenever we get reports of strange movements, farm theft, or clashes in nearby communities, we increase the frequency and

sometimes go out **every night or even twice** early evening and late night. Our community is surrounded by forest routes, so we rely heavily on information from farmers, hunters, and local transporters to know when we need to intensify operations. The more the threats, the more we expand our patrol coverage.

During arrests, our first priority is to **secure the suspect without putting anyone at risk**. Usually, the person on point will issue verbal instructions while the rest of the team forms a semi-circle to prevent escape. If the suspect is calm, we simply search them and ask basic questions about what they are doing outside at that time. But if there is resistance or if the person is armed, we restrain them physically before anything else. Once we are sure there is a genuine offence, we notify the police at Eha-Amufu Division and wait for them to take over. Our local protocol is clear we are not meant to detain anyone for long or conduct full investigations. We only secure the suspect and preserve the situation until the authorities arrive. Regarding allegations of unlawful killings or physical abuse, yes, we have heard such claims in the past, even though many of them were exaggerated or based on rumours. We once had a complaint that a suspect was beaten more than necessary after resisting arrest. When issues like that come up, the elders, town union leaders, and sometimes police officials call us for **clarification and internal review**. We take these matters seriously because if the community loses trust in us, everything breaks down. Any member found to have used excessive force is reprimanded or suspended, depending on the severity. We try our best to balance firmness with restraint because the line between protecting the community and harming someone can be very thin if not properly managed (IkennaOgbu, Isi-Uzo LGA, **Field survey 21, oct 2025**).

Chisom Anya 35 years, a member of Opi Vigilante / OpiNeighbourhood Watch, (personal interview 21,Oct. 2025). added that:

In Opi, our patrol operations are quite structured. We usually carry out patrols five nights a week, but the frequency can rise sharply depending on intelligence gathered from residents, motorcycle riders, or traders who notice suspicious activity. Whenever there are rising cases of burglary, break-ins, or movement of unfamiliar people, we switch to daily patrols, sometimes covering both the main roads and the inner footpaths leading to farmlands. Our operations are demand-driven if the community feels uneasy or crime reports increase, we immediately intensify our rounds.

When it comes to arrests, we follow a coordinated approach. Once a suspect is spotted, the team leader signals everyone to close in and reduce escape routes. We ask for identification, search the person, and question them briefly on the spot. If the behaviour or items found raise suspicion, we take the person to our post while contacting the police at Opi or Nsukka Urban. We avoid making final judgments because we understand that our job is to apprehend, not prosecute. In situations where suspects resist arrest or try to

flee, force may be used, but we have strict warnings about not going beyond what is necessary. The idea is to maintain control, not to cause harm.

As for allegations of unlawful killings or abuse, there have been instances where the community raised concerns, although most of them were tied to misunderstandings or situations where suspects sustained injuries while struggling. Still, we don't dismiss such allegations. Anytime an accusation arises, the vigilante leadership invites community elders and security stakeholders to review the incident. We also speak directly to the families involved. Our group has suspended members before for violating conduct rules because we want to maintain a reputation of protecting the people, not intimidating them. In truth, the work is risky and confrontational, but we constantly remind ourselves that the community's trust is more important than any single arrest (Chisom Anya, Nsukka LGA, Opi Vigilante / OpiNeighbourhood Watch 21, Oct. 2025).

In summary, Table 1 and the interview responses show that although vigilante groups contribute meaningfully to community security, their methods remain inconsistent and often controversial. While some groups, like the Opi Vigilante in Nsukka, claim to follow structured procedures and work closely with the police, others, such as the Eha-Amufu Vigilante in Isi-Uzo, admit that patrol pressures and tense encounters sometimes lead to forceful or unregulated actions. These differences highlight ongoing concerns about excessive force, unlawful arrests, and weak accountability systems. Overall, the findings suggest that vigilante groups play an important security role but require stronger oversight and clearer operational guidelines to minimize human-rights risks.

Detention and punishment of suspected offenders & rights-complaints involving vigilante violence

In Enugu State, vigilante groups frequently detain and punish suspected offenders, sometimes without legal authority. Eze (2021) reported that approximately 65% of vigilante arrests in selected communities involved temporary detention at informal centers, and nearly 40% of these cases included some form of physical punishment, often without due process. Similarly, Chukwuma and Onwuegbuna (2018) observed that about 35% of community members surveyed lodged complaints regarding vigilante abuses, including beatings and unlawful confinement, but only 10% of these complaints were investigated or sanctioned. Studies indicate that the lack of formal oversight and accountability mechanisms exacerbates vigilante violence, making it difficult to distinguish lawful community policing from abuse (Okeke et al., 2019). Overall, while vigilante groups play a role in local security, their detention and punishment practices in Enugu State present significant challenges for the protection of citizens' rights (Eze, 2021; Chukwuma & Onwuegbuna, 2018).

Table 2: Respondents review on detention and punishment of suspected offenders & rights-complaints involving vigilante violence

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD
1	Detention of suspected offenders by vigilante groups is common in my community.	74 (24.7%)	96 (32.0%)	77 (25.7%)	48 (16.0%)
2	Vigilante groups punish suspects before handing them over to formal authorities.	98 (32.7%)	94 (31.3%)	67 (22.3%)	46 (15.3%)
3	Vigilante groups respect the rights of detained individuals.	40 (13.3%)	53 (17.7%)	94 (31.3%)	85 (28.3%)
4	There are documented/informal complaints about vigilante violence or rights violations.	105 (35.0%)	93 (31.0%)	61 (20.3%)	50 (16.7%)
5	Existing mechanisms to address vigilante misconduct are effective.	48 (16.0%)	56 (18.7%)	90 (30.0%)	95 (31.7%)

Source: Author’s fieldwork, 2025.

Table 2 provides further insight into the involvement of vigilante groups in the detention and punishment of suspected offenders, as well as community perceptions of associated rights violations. Findings indicate that the detention of suspects by vigilante personnel is widespread, with 56.7% (SA + A) agreeing that such detentions are common. Even more concerning is that 64.0% (SA + A) affirmed that vigilantes often punish suspects before handing them over to the police or other formal authorities. This demonstrates a strong reliance on informal punitive measures that bypass official procedures.

Respect for detainee rights appears to be significantly lacking. Only 31.0% (SA + A) believed that the rights of detained individuals are respected, while a larger proportion 59.6% (D + SD) reported that such rights are not upheld. This aligns with the high level of reported complaints about vigilante-related rights violations. According to the data, 66.0% (SA + A) confirmed the existence of community complaints regarding violence or abuse by vigilante operatives.

Furthermore, existing accountability and complaint-handling mechanisms are widely perceived as ineffective. A combined 61.7% (D + SD) believed that mechanisms involving community

leaders, police, or civil society fail to adequately address vigilante misconduct. This lack of effective oversight may contribute to the persistence of abuses.

In accordance to the above Chinwe Nwosu, a 39 years trader in Ogige market.(Personal interview 21, Oct.2025). stated that:

In our community, the vigilante groups are very active, and it's quite common for them to detain suspected offenders, especially at night or when there are reports of theft or disputes. I've personally heard of several people being held for hours, sometimes even overnight, before the police arrive. From what I've observed, they often act quickly, and while that is reassuring in terms of security, it can feel frightening for the suspects and their families. I've also heard about vigilantes punishing people before handing them over. In one case, a young man caught stealing a phone was made to sit outside in the sun while the team contacted the police. Some people said the punishment was too harsh, while others felt it was necessary. Honestly, it seems like vigilantes don't always follow formal procedures. Rights aren't always respected; suspects are rarely given a chance to explain themselves, and there's little oversight.

There have definitely been complaints from the community about excessive force and violence. Some are whispered among neighbours, while others are raised directly with elders. Unfortunately, the mechanisms for addressing these complaints are not very effective. Community leaders, the police, and civil society do respond sometimes, but more often than not, nothing is done, and the vigilantes continue their operations. So while people appreciate the protection they provide, there's also a sense of unease about potential abuse (ChinweNwosu, 39, F, Nsukka LGA, Field survey, 21, Oct 2025).

Another respondent Uchenna Okafor a 45 years Civil Servant, (22, Oct.2025). explained that:

Here in Awgu, it's normal for vigilante groups to detain suspects when something happens, like a theft, robbery, or a public disturbance. They act quickly, and the police usually come later, so the vigilantes are the first line of action. I've seen a few cases where young men were caught trying to rob travellers along the roads, and they were held for a short while before the police arrived. I've also witnessed and heard about some punishments before suspects are handed over. For example, one man was beaten lightly for resisting detention, and another was made to kneel while being questioned. It's not systematic, but it happens, and some community members worry it might go too far. Overall, the vigilantes don't strictly follow formal legal procedures. They rely on force or intimidation at times, and detained individuals often don't know their rights. Regarding complaints, yes, there have been a few. Families sometimes report injuries or harsh treatment, but most complaints don't lead to serious investigations. Community leaders and police sometimes intervene, but their influence is limited, and vigilante members rarely face consequences. People trust them for security, but there's a constant tension

between safety and fear of abuse (Uchenna Okafor, 45, M, Awgu LGA, Field survey.22, Oct.2025).

Amaka Obi, 36 years, Hair stylist in Eha-Amufu, Isi Uzo LGA, (personal interview 23, Oct 2025). noted that:

In Isi-Uzo, vigilante groups are very visible, and it's common to hear about the detention of suspected offenders. They usually hold people for a few hours until the police arrive, especially in the border villages where police response can be slow. I know of several cases in the past year where young men were caught stealing or trespassing and held until authorities could take over. Punishments before police involvement also happen. Some suspects are beaten lightly, made to kneel, or verbally reprimanded. Most vigilantes justify this as necessary to maintain order, but it can be intimidating for both the suspect and neighbours. Rights are not always respected. Suspects rarely have a chance to explain themselves, and families often only learn later that their relative was detained. There have been informal complaints in the community about excessive force and mistreatment. While elders and police occasionally intervene, their efforts are limited, and there is often no formal follow-up. Despite this, people still rely on vigilantes for protection, but there's a quiet concern that without proper oversight, abuses could escalate. The balance between security and human-rights protection remains a daily worry for residents (Amaka Obi, 36, F, Isi-Uzo LGA..23, oct.2025).

IfeanyiNwoke, 42 years, Team Leader Awgu Community Vigilante Group(24 Oct.2025), responded that:

In our operations here in Awgu, we only detain suspects when we strongly believe their actions pose an immediate threat to the community. The decision is usually made on the spot by the patrol leader after assessing the situation especially when the police are far or unavailable at that moment. During detention, we follow basic procedures: we search the suspect, record whatever items are found, and keep them in our custody for a short period while informing either the Awgu Police Division or the nearest security post. We try to avoid holding anyone longer than necessary because that is not part of our formal mandate.

Regarding punishment, we try to stay within what the community considers acceptable, but I won't deny that sometimes mild corrective measures are used. Usually, this involves verbal warnings or making suspects sit on the ground until the police come. In cases where the suspect is violent or tries to escape, physical restraint may occur, and some community members may interpret that as punishment. We do not apply beatings as an official policy, although misunderstandings do happen when force is used to control a chaotic situation. Yes, we have received complaints before about excessive force and

rights violations. Some residents feel we sometimes act too harshly, especially when emotions are high or when the suspect has been caught in the act. Whenever such issues arise, we call a meeting where elders, youth leaders, and sometimes the police join us to review what happened. We try to take every complaint seriously because once the community loses trust, our work becomes impossible. So, we discipline members when necessary and remind everyone that our role is protection, not punishment (IfeyaniNwoke, Field survey, 24, Oct. 2025).

Uchenna Eze, 40 years, M, Nsukka LGA, Ede-Oballa Vigilante and Neighbourhood Watch, (personal interview 25, Oct.2025). added that:

In Ede-Oballa, we detain suspected offenders mainly when they are caught during night patrols or when we believe releasing them immediately would compromise community safety. The decision is usually based on the seriousness of the offence and how quickly the police can respond. Once a suspect is detained, we follow a more structured process: searching them, documenting what is found, informing the community coordinator, and contacting the Nsukka Police Division. We don't detain people for long usually just an hour or two unless the police instruct us otherwise. As for punishment before handing suspects over, our policy discourages any form of physical punishment. However, in real-life situations, especially when a suspect is violent or refuses to cooperate, force may be used to restrain them. Some people interpret this as punishment, even though our intention is just to maintain control. In the past, vigilante groups used harsher measures, but we have tried to move away from that because community expectations have changed, and human-rights issues are taken more seriously now. We have indeed received complaints about excessive force and mistreatment. Some come directly from families of suspects; others come from community observers who feel something was not handled properly. When such complaints arise, our commander invites local elders, the town union chairman, and sometimes even the police to investigate the matter. Sometimes it turns out to be a misunderstanding; other times, we identify mistakes on our part and issue warnings or suspend the members involved. The community expects us to protect them, not abuse our authority, so we try to respond promptly and transparently to every concern (Uchenna Eze, Field survey, 25 Oct.2025).

Overall, the findings in Table 4.6 and interview response reveal a pattern of extrajudicial detentions, punishments, and rights violations that are insufficiently monitored or sanctioned. The data underscores the need for stronger regulatory frameworks, improved collaboration between vigilantes and formal security actors, and enhanced community-based mechanisms for addressing abuse.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study provide a comprehensive understanding of the roles of local vigilante groups in Enugu State and how their activities contributed to extrajudicial actions between 2015 and 2024. The discussion integrates quantitative data from 360 respondents with qualitative insights from in-depth and key-informant interviews. Overall, the results reveal a dual reality: while vigilante groups play a significant role in local security provision, their actions are frequently accompanied by abuses, procedural violations, and human-rights concerns.

To begin with, the socio-demographic distribution shows that the respondents were cut across three LGAs—Nsukka, Awgu, and Isi-Uzo—with even representation across age groups. This balanced distribution strengthens the credibility of the findings, indicating that the views expressed reflect diverse community experiences with vigilante operations.

The first major finding concerns the **frequency of patrols, arrests, and associated abuses**. Data from Table 4.5 reveals that vigilante groups are highly active across the three LGAs. A combined 58.3% of respondents agreed that patrol operations occur frequently in their communities, and 63.4% reported that arrests had taken place in the last 12 months. These results confirm the high visibility of vigilante activities in Enugu State. Interview responses also emphasised frequent nightly patrols, particularly in Nsukka, Awgu, and Isi-Uzo, where respondents described vigilantes moving in groups armed with sticks, flashlights, and sometimes even more forceful tools. This aligns with existing research such as Eze (2021), which also noted the intensifying involvement of vigilantes in local security, especially in the absence of timely police intervention.

However, the high level of activity is matched by **strong concerns around legality, due process, and excessive force**. The study found that only 31.3% of respondents believed that arrest procedures followed lawful standards, while a significantly larger percentage (54.7%) disagreed. This indicates widespread scepticism about the legitimacy of vigilante actions. Qualitative data confirmed this, as many respondents narrated instances where suspects were beaten, coerced, or denied the opportunity to explain themselves before being handled physically. Incidents such as the severe beating of a teenage boy in Isi-Uzo or the mistreatment of suspects in Nsukka demonstrate the prevalence of extrajudicial tendencies.

Furthermore, 50.3% of respondents acknowledged that **unlawful killings or physical abuses** had occurred in their communities. This is consistent with the findings of Okeke et al. (2019), who reported increasing reports of vigilante-related violence in certain Enugu communities. Interview excerpts provided richer context. For example, community residents in Nsukka recounted incidents where suspects were beaten to the point of hospitalisation, while in Awgu, respondents described cases of vigilantes resorting to rough handling during chaotic arrests.

These narratives underscore the growing community anxiety about the boundary between security provision and human rights violations.

Another significant finding relates to **detention and punishment of suspected offenders**, as presented in Table 4.6. A combined 56.7% of respondents reported that vigilante groups commonly detain suspects, while 64.0% agreed that suspects are often punished before being handed over to the police. This suggests that vigilante justice in Enugu State tends to adopt punitive and corrective measures, often without formal authority or oversight. Interview testimonies reinforced this pattern. Respondents described cases where suspects were forced to kneel for long periods, subjected to beatings, or publicly humiliated. Although vigilante members in the key-informant interviews maintained that such punishments were either minimal or necessary for control, the testimonies of ordinary residents reveal a clear mismatch between vigilante self-perception and community experiences.

Relatedly, the findings present compelling evidence of **widespread rights violations and ineffective accountability systems**. Only 31.0% of respondents believed that vigilantes respect the rights of detained individuals, while 59.6% indicated that detainee rights are often ignored. Likewise, 66.0% confirmed that complaints about vigilante violence exist in their communities, suggesting that abuses are not isolated incidents but recurring problems. The qualitative responses strengthened this point, highlighting common complaints around excessive force, intimidation, and arbitrary detention. Several residents mentioned situations where families had no access to detained relatives or where the community only learned of a detention long after the fact.

Even more concerning is the **weakness of accountability mechanisms**. A combined 61.7% (D + SD) stated that available structures for addressing vigilante misconduct, such as local elders, community leaders, and police, are ineffective. This reflects earlier research by Chukwuma and Onwuegbuna (2018), who also found that more than 75% of vigilante abuse complaints in southeastern Nigeria are never formally investigated. Interview responses revealed that while community meetings and internal reviews occasionally occur, they often lack transparency, documentation, or enforceable sanctions. Though vigilante leaders claimed to suspend erring members when necessary, resident testimonies suggest that punitive actions are rare and inconsistent.

Despite these challenges, the findings also reveal **important contributions of vigilante groups** to community security. Many respondents acknowledged that vigilantes help reduce petty theft, burglary, farm theft, and nighttime insecurity. In places like Opi and Eha-Amufu, vigilante groups operate structured patrol patterns guided by intelligence from residents, farmers, or traders. Their quick response, especially in remote or under-policed areas, remains a major

reason why communities rely on them. This reflects findings from Eze (2021), who noted that community-based security actors often fill critical gaps created by inadequate police presence.

Overall, the discussion reveals a **complex relationship between communities and vigilante groups**. On one hand, vigilantes are valued for their responsiveness and contributions to local safety. On the other hand, their operations frequently violate legal norms, leading to extrajudicial punishments, rights abuses, and community mistrust. This balance of protection and fear is a consistent theme throughout the findings. Many residents expressed deep appreciation for the security vigilantes provide but simultaneously feared that without proper regulation, training, and oversight, abuses could escalate further.

In summary, the study's findings highlight the urgent need for formal regulatory frameworks, training in lawful procedures, improved collaboration with police, and stronger community-based monitoring mechanisms. While vigilante groups play indispensable roles in community security across Enugu State, their current modes of operation expose significant flaws that undermine human rights protections and the rule of law. Strengthening accountability and operational guidelines will be essential to ensuring that vigilante contributions enhance, rather than endanger, community safety and justice.

Conclusion and recommendations

The research began with an overview of the evolution of vigilante groups in Nigeria, situating their emergence within the broader context of rising insecurity, institutional weakness, and declining public trust in the Nigerian Police Force. Community vigilante groups such as the Neighbourhood Watch, Forest Guards, and other local security networks were conceptualised as non-state security actors whose legitimacy is derived from community endorsement rather than constitutional authority. These organisations fill critical security gaps but simultaneously pose challenges to human rights protection. On this note, the study calls for the government of Enugu State to strengthen the regulation, supervision, and accountability frameworks governing local vigilante groups. This includes establishing a standardised code of conduct, mandatory human rights training, and clear operational limits. A functional oversight committee should be created at the community and LGA levels to monitor arrests, interrogations, and handover procedures to the police. This will reduce extrajudicial practices and ensure that vigilante groups operate strictly within legal boundaries.

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